

MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE UNESCO CHAIR IN THE PRESERVATION AND MANAGEMENT OF HISTORICAL CENTERS OF SAMARKAND STATE ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION UNIVERSITY (SAMSACU)

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Abstract

The UNESCO Chair in the Preservation and Management of Historical Centers at Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University (SamSACU) has become a central figure in cultural heritage preservation in Central Asia. Established to tackle the challenges of preserving historical sites and promoting sustainable urban development, the Chair has successfully enhanced academic collaboration, launched innovative educational programs, and conducted significant research.

Key initiatives include the creation of a Master's program that incorporates environmental risk assessment into its curriculum, as well as the organization of international conferences and workshops that foster dialogue among experts. The Chair supports these efforts through scientific publications that contribute to the field of heritage conservation.

Moreover, the Chair has invested in advanced technological equipment to improve research capabilities and conservation practices. Through collaborations and capacity-building projects funded by ERASMUS and DAAD, the UNESCO Chair is poised to influence the future of cultural heritage management in Uzbekistan and Central Asia, with plans for new partnerships and projects to further its impact on the preservation of historical urban landscapes.

Key words: preservation, historical centers, cultural heritage, interdisciplinary approach, capacity building, international collaboration, academic network, exchange programs, research, conservation.

Achievement 1: Strengthening Professional Networks

The UNESCO Chair in the Preservation and Management of Historical Centers at Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University (SamSACU) has made significant strides in broadening and strengthening its professional network through strategic partnership agreements with 43 universities worldwide. Notable collaborations include esteemed institutions such as Turin Polytechnic University (Italy), Tajik Technical University, Islamic University of Indonesia, and several Uzbek universities, including Bukhara Engineering Technological Institute, Bukhara State University, Samarkand State University, and Tashkent University of Architecture and Engineering, as well as the University of Applied Sciences Potsdam.

The sustainability of these partnerships has been enhanced by successful grant applications from ERASMUS and DAAD, which have facilitated an interdisciplinary approach emphasizing innovative methods in the preservation of Uzbekistan's cultural heritage and the maintenance of urban and social environments within local communities (mahalla). Faculty and students of the UNESCO Chair have actively participated in international academic events, such as the German-Uzbek Summer School in Bukhara (2022) and the Summer School on "A Holiday Village and Facilities at Bamboo Studies Center Area" in Yogyakarta, Indonesia (2023). Moreover, students have received accolades for their contributions in international competitions, including graduation projects and master's theses organized by Pacific State University in Khabarovsk, Russia. These initiatives

reflect the Chair's commitment to enhancing academic collaboration and advancing the field of heritage preservation.

Achievement 2: Launching the Master's Program in Cultural Heritage Preservation.

The UNESCO Chair in the Preservation and Management of Historical Centers at Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University (SamSACU) successfully launched a Master's program titled "Preservation and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects" as part of the EU-funded project "Environmental Risk Assessment and Mitigation on Cultural Heritage Assets in Central Asia." This initiative involves collaboration with esteemed partners, including Turin Polytechnic University (Italy), Bauhaus University Weimar (Germany), Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek (Croatia), Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent (Uzbekistan), the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Tajikistan, Khujand Polytechnic Institute of Tajik Technical University, and Tajik Technical University named after Academician M. Osimi. The Master's program adopts an interdisciplinary approach to environmental risk assessment and mitigation concerning cultural heritage assets in Central Asia. In the preparatory phase, the UNESCO Chair conducted a thorough investigation of local needs across Central Asian nations, with a particular emphasis on environmental risks. These findings were instrumental in shaping a comprehensive curriculum for the 120 ECTS Master's program. Furthermore, the Chair established a free access digital library that houses an extensive array of teaching materials, including books, hypertexts, videos, and best practices, thereby

enhancing educational resources available to students and researchers. As part of a broader network of specialized research centers in the region, the UNESCO Chair has also inaugurated the ERAMCA CENTER (Environmental Risk Assessment and Mitigation on Cultural Heritage Assets in Central Asia), which serves as a dedicated laboratory focused on advancing research and methodologies in this critical area.

Achievement 3: Application of cutting edge knowledge to the conservation of cultural heritage objects.

The UNESCO Chair in the Preservation and Management of Historical Centers has formalized a cooperation agreement with the Department of Preservation of Cultural Heritage at Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University (SamSACU) to undertake joint research on the landscapes of historical cities in Uzbekistan. This collaborative initiative aims to conduct comprehensive inventory research focusing on both cultural and natural landscapes within the historical centers of the country.

Through this agreement, the Chair's staff will employ advanced methodologies and cutting-edge knowledge in conservation to systematically document and analyze these landscapes. The anticipated outcomes of this research are expected to inform the development of local master plans, serving as practical tools for municipal authorities in Uzbekistan. By integrating research findings into urban planning processes, this initiative seeks to enhance the sustainable preservation of Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage while addressing contemporary challenges faced by local communities.

Achievement 4: Organization and Participation in Academic Conferences and Workshops

The UNESCO Chair in the Preservation and Management of Historical Centers has significantly contributed to academic discourse by hosting three international conferences: "Urgent Problems of Improving the System of Personnel Training in the Architectural and Construction Areas" (Samarkand, November 8, 2023), "Sustainable Architecture: Challenges and Achievements of the Present and Future" (Samarkand, May 18–19, 2023), and "Focus on Tourism & Creative Economy" (Samarkand, June 22–23, 2023). These events provided a platform for scholars and practitioners to engage in critical discussions regarding contemporary issues in architecture, urban planning, and cultural heritage management.

In addition to the conferences, the Chair organized two specialized workshops. The first, titled "Study of Traditional Dwellings in the Historical Environment of the Gur Emir Mausoleum," featured renowned international experts from Turkey, including Architect and Restorator Ebru Pekgoz and City Planner Haydar Pekgoz, held from August 6 to 30, 2023. The second workshop, "Practices in Design Studios," included insights from Turkish expert Gozde Qizilkan and took place from July 17 to August 11, 2023.

Moreover, faculty members affiliated with the UNESCO Chair have published seven articles in

international peer-reviewed journals, contributing to the body of knowledge in the field. Notable publications include "Study of Traditional Makhalla in the Historical Environment of Samarkand" by L. Rahimov and "Proposals for the Restoration and Preservation of the Historicity of Samarkand" by A.S. Uralov. These scholarly outputs underscore the Chair's commitment to advancing research and enhancing academic collaboration in heritage preservation and architectural studies.

Achievement 5: Support for Scientific Publications

The UNESCO Chair in the Preservation and Management of Historical Centers has actively facilitated the dissemination of research findings through the support of various scientific publications. This initiative aims to contribute to the academic discourse surrounding architectural preservation and urban planning in Uzbekistan.

Notable publications include "XXI Century New Cities: New Approaches and Opportunities" and "Utopian Comprehensiveness" by Prof. A.B. Balgayev, which explore contemporary urban development strategies. Dr. Laziz Rahimov's article, "Study of Traditional Makhalla in the Historical Environment of Samarkand," examines the cultural significance of traditional neighborhoods within the historical context of the city.

Furthermore, significant contributions to the field of conservation are represented in the works "Conservation of Tilla Kori Madrasa Portal in Samarkand" and "Conservation of Shohi Zinda Entrance Portal in Samarkand," both authored by Prof. O.X. Urokov in collaboration with Dr. D.B. Bozorboeva and Dr. G.R. Umarova, respectively. These studies highlight critical restoration efforts aimed at preserving the integrity of significant cultural landmarks.

Additionally, Prof. A.S. Uralov's publication, "Proposals for the Preservation of the Historic City of Samarkand," presents strategies for maintaining the city's historical character. Lastly, the collaborative work "Innovative Solutions in the Development of City Planning in Samarkand," co-authored by Prof. G. Shukurov et al., addresses contemporary challenges in urban planning through innovative methodologies.

Through these scholarly contributions, the UNESCO Chair not only enhances the visibility of research in heritage preservation but also fosters an environment of academic collaboration and knowledge sharing within the field.

Achievement 6: Acquisition of Advanced Equipment

The UNESCO Chair in the Preservation and Management of Historical Centers has significantly enhanced its research capabilities through the acquisition of advanced technological equipment. This includes the procurement of a 3D laser scanner, thermal imaging devices (teplovizor), and ten high-capacity computers, among other essential tools.

These state-of-the-art technologies enable the Chair to conduct research-based conservation of cultural heritage objects with greater precision and efficiency. The 3D laser scanner facilitates detailed documentation and analysis of architectural features, allowing for accurate modeling and restoration planning. The thermal imaging devices provide valuable insights into structural integrity and thermal performance, essential for assessing the conservation needs of historical sites.

By integrating these advanced tools into its research methodologies, the UNESCO Chair is better equipped to address the complexities of cultural heritage preservation, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities in this vital field. This investment not only supports the Chair's academic objectives but also enhances its role as a leader in the application of innovative conservation practices.

The UNESCO Chair in the Preservation and Management of Historical Centers at Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University (SamSACU) coordinates partnerships with 18 countries across Europe and Asia, including 8 South Asian nations. Its primary functions involve the development of exchange programs, summer schools, and capacity-building trainings.

The Chair has participated in two Erasmus+ capacity-building projects aimed at transferring EU best practices to the Central Asian region during 2022-2023. Additionally, it has successfully engaged in a DAAD-funded project titled “Interdisciplinary at the

Monument,” which focused on innovative methods and practical research for the preservation of Uzbekistan's cultural heritage. This project facilitated student and staff mobility and culminated in the organization of the German-Uzbek Summer School in 2022. The DAAD has approved a second phase of this project for early 2024, further strengthening the collaboration.

Furthermore, a representative from the UNESCO Chair is involved with the Agency of Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Department of Cultural Heritage of Samarkand Region. Plans are underway to sign a new cooperation agreement in 2024 with TIKA (Turkish Cooperation and Collaboration Agency) and IICAS (International Institute for Central Asian Studies) to further study historical urban landscapes in Central Asia.

Conclusion

Through these initiatives, the UNESCO Chair is not only advancing academic and practical knowledge in the field of cultural heritage preservation but also fostering international collaboration that enhances educational opportunities and capacity building in Central Asia. This proactive engagement underscores the Chair's commitment to promoting sustainable practices and innovative approaches in the preservation of historical centers, ultimately contributing to the region's cultural heritage and academic landscape.

References

1. <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/603/>
2. <https://international.samdaqu.edu.uz/>

